

Uses and Effect of 'Open Data' on Political Communication in Pakistan

(A Context to Electronic Media)

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Abstract

Any country's future success depends on ongoing development projects. They must ensure that their citizens live in a safe and healthy sociopolitical environment. However, it varies from region to region. As a country with a small economy, Pakistan cannot guarantee the safety of its people. As a result, the government can focus on what is best for its citizens through various methods. The open data system forces the authority to provide access to data to the public in real time. After the Right to Information Act 2016 was promulgated, it is essential for organizations to make their data accessible to public within real time. It is one of these critical developments initiated within Pakistan's framework that provides massive access to data bases and data sets of public interest. People can make progress in their lives by consulting databases that are available online. It broadens their horizons and encourages them to think creatively. It also gives them the chance to sharpen their learning abilities and accept the concession of taking things from their resources and use them completely. It's a win-win situation. When using private data sources, it's important to keep in mind that not all data is secure. Open data is critical to allowing people to get input and use it in the right way. Using available data systems in the journalism to assess the impact on Pakistani political communication is the focus of this research. For the sake of preventing corruption, open data systems are essential in journalism across the country. To put it another way, the systems in place encourage national institutions to take accountability seriously. As a result, there is a probability of witnessing corruption that destabilizes society. Increasing innovation and creativity requires the use of open data systems. The availability of these resources has been shown to play a significant role in establishing a trend of innovative growth. The positive impact of 'Open Data' on Pakistani political communication, particularly in the context of electronic media, is widely observed.

Keywords: *Open Data, Pakistan, Sources, Government, People, Media, Journalists.*

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Introduction

To succeed in the era of technology, every nation needs to experience digitally advanced projects. They must ensure that their citizens live in a healthy social atmosphere that will provide them with stability. As a country, Pakistan is a struggling economy that cannot easily offer its citizens the kind of protection they need. For this reason, different policies have been emphasized, enabling the government to look for the citizens' good. One of the main innovations that have been introduced within the context of Pakistan's establishment is the open data structure, which offers tremendous access to databases. The research looks at the pros and cons of utilizing available data structures from Pakistan's viewpoint to assess their impact on Pakistan's social and political progress. The use of the open data structure is beneficial for citizens to carry out their everyday tasks in life; it is necessary to prevent corruption and encourage a high degree of transparency of national agencies. Accessible data structures mean that users are willing to access data about diverse study subjects. Open Data in the form of freely available data to anyone and can be reached by any person. Numerous countries around the globe utilize such open data policies to promote accountability. If a corporation openly publishes the statistics, there is a reasonable probability that everybody can see its findings (Attard, 2016). As Obama launched a movement to maintain openness and integrity in this regime, this initiative was successfully initiated in the United States. Open data policy has been commonly utilized and used for this reason to guarantee that civic agencies can function successfully. Pakistan has indeed followed and implemented this in order to introduce the pattern and philosophy of openness here. Strengthening the position of civil society and people was the main impetus for implementing this open data framework. It was undertaken to ensure their presence in the country's social growth. It was not only good for socioeconomic growth but also important to add social empowerment to the nation as well. The government has primarily employed it to recognize people's rights to know how their money is being spent. In order to satisfy their needs, the governments in Pakistan have used this open data policy (Judge, 2005). For a developing world like Pakistan, such programs are also a strong excuse for governments to work successfully and efficiently.

Fig 1: *Open Government Framework*

Background of the study

It is important to look at the past of these systems in order to appreciate the effect of open data frameworks in the sense of democratic communication. Back in 2010, one might take a look at the initiation of these types of programs that enabled the country to implement and start its open data framework. While the usage of these open frameworks has been associated with many problems, they are still being used because of their utmost importance in the management of governance systems. In Pakistan, these structures are widespread and are also used in various other nations. Because of their immense value, countries tend to use those structures in order to remain out of the kind of abuse that their nation might propagate. It is also indeed a smart policy to utilize these types of structures and to ensure that they play a significant role in the success of their nation by enhancing its social and political framework, G.D.P., and economic development with openness. It is also anticipated that the opening up of government knowledge would contribute to the founding of new organizations. Accessible information would undoubtedly arise from unrestricted access to information for citizens and open division groups, as compared to the usage of chargeable information properties as an ability to increase the effectiveness of administrative arrangements. The importance of this research is to have a significant effect on the political communication of the Pakistan. One should ensure that one has a strong transparency mechanism in order to make tremendous success. Pakistan will reach the desired level of progress by engagement in both social and cultural growth through the introduction of this 'Accessible Data' scheme. It has had an immense effect

on the growth of the social and political sector, as it gives easy access to investigative journalist to report the story.

Problem Statement

In industrialized countries like Pakistan, open data structures are effective, so this study considers the disruptive position of emerging economies like Pakistan. The key aim of the research, therefore, is to calculate the social growth that emerges from the presence of these accessible data structures. The analysis represents the efficacy of this structure in Pakistani society, mainly on social and political issues and the country's social growth, with specific regard to the viewpoint of political communication.

Research Questions

1. How will open data structures be beneficial for the Pakistan social and political development?
2. How will the usage of these open data structures allow the nation to achieve social and political growth by supplying citizens with beneficial policies?
3. In ensuring accountability, how can an open data framework play a role?

Research Objectives

1. To accessible the impact of 'Open Data' in context to Political Communication in electronic media.
2. The aim of the study is to quantify and deeply evaluate the value of performing case studies in Pakistan from the viewpoint of electronic media and to the political progress in Pakistan.
3. Determining the position of the transparent framework of data in ensuring accountability.

Research Hypothesis

H1: The social and political growth with context to media and the usage of the open data framework in Pakistan have a positive impact.

H2: The usage of an accessible data framework helps boost an impact in political communication of electronic media in Pakistan.

H3: The more openly accessible Data is available, the more openness and transparent development will be generated in different news program of electronic media.

Literature Review

Important accessible component data, which is often commonly used by businesses, contains, for instance, spatial, environment, statistical, business, traffic, and administrative details. In March 2011, the Finnish government laid out priorities to improve the re-use of free records as one of the main components of the Government Programme. Provoked by these ambitions, in 2012, government associations began opening up their data holdings. In May 2012, the National Land

Survey of Finland opened up its sophisticated topographic details. After a year, by means of its online administration, the Finnish Meteorological Institute opened up

climate information. The aim is to open up by 2020 all notable knowledge materials acquired and preserved by the open organization, rendering them available and functional in machine-comprehensible arrangements, within simple terms of use and for nothing out of pocket. In Europe, the United Kingdom has been the first nation to open up public data and has accomplished a significant amount of positive social and economic growth results.

Methodology and Data Analysis

Descriptive and analytical ways of gathering data are also used. The polling technique for interviews and surveys is used, and data obtained from four user groups, namely industry, media, public, and NGOs. The thesis included a deductive methodology that implemented a top-down method. Correlation includes mathematical research: regression Review and Factor Review. The findings found that the usage of open data platforms affected Pakistan social and political development with context to electronic media.

Fig 2: News Channel Ratings

Discussion

Open Data System

If anyone is allowed to use it for free, such kind of data is called open data. There are several features relevant to the usage of open data structures, including it is open to multiple individuals to access and evaluate, the data can be used to read, scan and sort content, and it can easily be related to other web applications. Accessible data structures may be able to enable nations to learn how to make the most use of their wealth and how to make a change (Mohan, 2014). With the help of technology advancement, organizations are recognizing the advantages of open data, such as the European Union's "Open Data Portal," Pakistan's "Opening Government" campaign and the Global Open Data Index, which all aim to collect

and make widely accessible vast amounts of information about the industrial, educational, research, medical, and employment sectors.

According to the Open Data Barometer project, none of the 77 nation that are evaluated, conducted a comprehensive analysis of the effect of data opening in 2013. The absence of effective accumulation of information and arrangement of insights regarding the use of information is a noteworthy purpose behind this. With the OVC ('Virtual Office of Cadastre') established in March 2003, Spain was able to make all of its geographic information available to the public for free. By shipping IDEE geo-portal in June 2004, the knowledge opening phase continued to expand the usefulness of geographic information. When comparing 2004 to 2005, the number of people who used maps increased by 700% (from over a million uses to more than 41 million). Over 124 million people made this request in 2010 than in 2004.

Fig 3: *Open Government Cycle*

Improved Transparency with Open Data

The in-time availability of a transparent framework is dependent on it. This can improve transparency as a focal point, e.g., how the Government in Britain uses taxpayer's excises and taxes. In this respect, greater openness should be called for by such organizations such as Open Societies so as to monitor the accountability regime and how the branches of the estate are paying across Europe. The impact of open spatial information was surveyed by Ahonen-Rainio et al. (2014). Their study reveals insight into the methods for the use, significance, and benefits of customer geographic information, but it does not look at surveying its financial impacts in terms of euro. According to Koski (2011)'s empirical analysis, the opening of geographical information and a shift toward using negligible cost valuation was associated with fundamentally faster deals' development for companies in structural and building exercises and related specialized consultancy divisions in 15 countries. Data from 531 Finnish organizations was used in a study by Koski (2012) to determine the average age of new information-based products and services in those organizations. The findings suggests that companies specializing in intellectual endeavors such as research and development, land acquisition, or creation are more

likely than others to make significant contributions to the field of information technology and management.

Small businesses, particularly in their products and administrations, can quickly benefit from newly released data, according to meetings by Kiuru et al. (2012).

Fig 4: Open Data Impact on People's Lives

Source: <https://www.opengovguide.com/topics/open-government-data/>

People's lives are impacted in three ways by accessible data programs: 1) Strengthening democracy by having government more transparent than ever, making the country better enough and capable, and enhancing public services (Stefaan & Andrew, n.a.). 2) Empowering the inhabitants-this action is followed by regulating the public's lifestyles. 3) Introduction of new economic opportunities: individuals and organizations can obtain more transparency throughout cities or remote areas to stimulate social prosperity and to open up new industry verticals.

Impact of Open Data Sets on the Globally

The usage of an open data framework is very beneficial for countries to determine what is wrong with their policies. So, they should appreciate the approaches they should overcome the problems they encounter. Therefore, it is an important way to guarantee that this will be exploited for useful purposes to provide recourse to access data sets. It can be found from evaluating various surveys performed by different countries about the effect of open data (Hobley, 2012): there is a government platform in India in which Open Data is used in India, Data.gov is an open data platform in the United States, has the potential to contain different forms of data within it, data.gov.au in Australia offers access to any kind of info, data.govt in New Zealand.

In Spain in 2012, over 150 organizations operated primarily in the field of "infomediary," providing services using transparent knowledge. At the moment, the section used about 4,000 employees, and the annual estimate of these departments

was calculated at EUR 330-500 million. For, e.g., the Weather Channel and Garmin, a big organization in G.P.S. advertising, were founded in the United States using crude open knowledge. The reasonable valuation of Garmin in 2013 was more than USD 7 billion (Capgemini Consulting, 2013; The Open Data Economy). Climate Corp., founded in 2006, offers another example of bridling crude accessible data for business use. Initially, temperature and harvest gauge knowledge was collected for environmental security purposes. Subsequently, the company expanded the usage of such data to assist with sowing plans. Atmosphere Corp. was offered for USD 930 million in the harvest era of 2013.

Open Data Principles

The Open-Data Charter (2015) listed the following principles:

- Data transparency by default
- Open and available
- Ready to share valuable Data
- For improved governance and the commitment of citizens
- For sustainable creativity
- Promptly, suitable and all-inclusive.

The Open Data Governance Model

Fig 5: *Open Government Model*

Political Communication and Pakistani Electronic Media

Knowing this historical background and having a peek into Pakistan's past

would allow us to further examine the Pakistan case study in the light of Pakistan's social growth. This is also plausible since Pakistan has adopted the Pakistan government pattern of parliament or legislature since its freedom.

There are several social problems faced by Pakistan as a third world nation. For example, gender disparity, the emancipation of women, education of children (particularly girls), malnutrition, inflation, corruption, economic unrest, border law and order status, and border insecurity, etc. Pakistan will successfully solve the situation by implementing the 'Shared Data' framework like the United Kingdom to address all these societal problems and challenges. The Pakistan 'Open Data' framework model is highly productive for the growth of Pakistan. This method makes it easy to tackle society's ills in real-time and to have a rational response. As the analysis demonstrates the social progress of Pakistan, the same is possible for Pakistan owing to 'Open Records.' In Pakistani electronic media, the news usually get more attention when addressing political issues. The following five are major issues covered in Pakistani talk shows as analyze by viewership.

1. Corruption: Open Data's utmost and chief strength is that it aims to control corruption. Through the capacity of real-time transparency, through monitoring any wrongdoing with public records, the framework renders officials liable. With the passage of the right to information act bill by Pakistan's parliament in 2016, the government is limiting itself to opening up all public records. Corruption today is probably the greatest danger to the country's economic prosperity. The National Accountability Bureau (N.A.B.) has its own cyber arm, as well as the Federal Investigation Agency (F.I.A.).

2. Terrorism: The biggest problem in Pakistan, along with corruption, is the terrorism, and innovative measures should be used to fight it. Open Data helps track terrorism activity and encourages officials to respond abruptly to the signs of terrorist activities. Since 9/11, when Pakistan became a non-NATO partner of the fight on terrorism, multiple militant incidents have taken millions of precious lives in the world, becoming the core of the war zone. The country's thin tank prepares several counter-terrorism measures and is one of them utilizing the 'Shared Data' framework.

3. Election: Election is a two-sided mechanism where there is a nominee on one hand, and public on the other hand. Recently, the latest census has raised several concerns about the transparency of public counting. The influence of the public is seen less in many Punjab and K.P.K. villages than it really is. 'Accessible data' plays a significant role in illustrating the community of individuals in every area. NADRA can play a key role in this. It would be conveniently manageable to know how many citizens reside in a given area once the data becomes available.

4. Health & Education: Pakistan is still lagging behind when it comes to health and quality education in terms of both the numbers and the expectations. An

easy-to-access database can provide real-time information on everything from school enrollment and student performance to the location of hospitals and their medical staff. The difference between the number of boys and girls in

school is around 10 points, based on government figures for 2017, from 5th grade (nine years old) to 12th grade (17 years old). After the last elections in 2013, these statistics have hardly improved. A large number of students, both boys and girls, drop out at the primary level in government high schools. "The lack of secondary or higher-level schools is one of the major factors contributing to the drop in post-primary enrollment," says Aleena Khan of AlifAilaan, a non-profit educational organization in Pakistan. Literacy rates are also low in comparison to neighboring countries. In addition, Bangladesh, which separated from Pakistan in 1971, has a higher literacy rate. In combating illiteracy in Pakistan, the Open Data structure will help. The map below illustrates the paradigm change in the country's literacy rate by the usage of technical resources.

5. Cyber Crime: Several different problems are emerging with the rising influence of social media. During the Fifth Generation War, that is a new hybrid war between India and Pakistan, social media is playing an increasingly important role. 'Free Data,' for example, can easily combat cybercrime like Internet abuse, bullying or abusing someone, or stealing their data without their permission. Pakistan's outcome demonstrates that this is also possible in Pakistan. Any operation commissioned in the virtual domain by computers, digital devices, and networks and promoted through the internet medium. By illegal trespassing into unauthorized remote networks around the globe, it may involve the distant stealing of information belonging to a person, government, or private sector. This entails taking millions of rupees from the online bank to bullying cyber consumers and stalking them. Cyber Fraud also involves transmitting malware or publishing defamation posts to various systems. Cyber-crime panels should be: A) As a violent moneymaker, internet criminality has already exceeded illicit drug dealing. B) As a consequence of cybercrime, someone's identification is compromised every 3 seconds. C) The vulnerable P.C. will get compromised within four minutes of connecting to the Internet without a sophisticated protection kit. Social engineering is a tool used to gain access to classified details through cybercriminals. In the case of social engineering, attackers utilize coercion and deception to manipulate victims into exposing sensitive details. Data fraud is the act of obtaining computer-based information from an unknown victim in order to violate their privacy or obtain sensitive details. For individual computer users, as well as large corporate companies, data-stealing is progressively a problem. In data-stealing situations, the following types are most common. Identity theft relates to a crime in which an individual maliciously obtains and utilizes the personal/sensitive details of another person to conduct fraud/scams while utilizing the stolen identity. This offense is usually conducted for economic benefit. Through extracting e-mail addresses, saving data on server databases, eavesdropping through the networks to get hold of transactions, the cybercriminal gains access to an individual's records. With the aid of 'Free Records,' all these offenses can be solved quickly. Countries such as Pakistan have achieved so effectively.

Fig 6: Rating of Prime-Time Programs in Electronic Media (Pakistan)

What Are the 'Open Data' Obstacles in Pakistan?

The most challenging thing in Pakistan is the use of 'Free Data' without knowing what it is. When it comes to any beneficial application of technology, the government's non-serious approach persists. To combat diseases, all developing countries are now incorporating modern interactive technologies into their economies. Pakistan also lags behind other developed countries in terms of technology utilization. There are many bright minds in Pakistan who achieve success in technology, without a doubt on a personal level, but there is no incentive or encouragement for them on a national level. However, more positive changes will be made if professional journalists are taught how to use 'Free Data.'

Conclusion & Recommendations

Of course, the push towards accessible data structures has a significant impact on higher institutions, for example, at the government level, so that knowledge is made clear and usable for social and political changes. The following are methods for improving government data accessibility, including:

Public understanding about current developments. Involve the general public and strengthen their engagement by exchanging knowledge.

The creation of a standard valuation system such that a person's worth may be calculated.

Conducting science analysis so that Data is used to assess innovation.

Bibliography

- Buckingham, D. (2012). The electronic generation? Children and new media. In L. A. Lievrouw & S. Livingstone (Eds.), *Handbook of new media: Social shaping and consequences of I.C.T.s* (pp. 77-88). London: Sage.
- Gross, E.F., Juvonen, J., Gable, S.L. (2002). Internet use and well-being in adolescence. *Journal of Social Issues*, 58, 75-90.
- Pantic I., 2014, Online Social Networking and Mental Health, CYBERPSYCHOLOGY, BEHAVIOR, AND SOCIAL NETWORKING, Volume 17, Number 10, 2014, DOI: 10.1089/cyber.2014.0070
- Shabbir, T., M Nadeemullah. (2020). Impact of 'Open Data' and its Effectiveness for Pakistan Social Issues: Learning from the U.K. Experience, 25(1), 253-272. Retrieved from <https://journal.psc.edu.pk/index.php/pp/article/view/395>
- Halonen, A, Being Open about Data. Analysis of the PAKISTAN open data policies and applicability of open data. *The Finnish Institute in London*, (2014).
- Hogge, B. Open Data Study. *Transparency and Accountability Initiative*. (2019)
- Jones, B. & Norton, P. *Politics PAKISTAN*. London: Routledge, (2014).
- Judge, D. *Political Institutions in the United Kingdom*. London: Oxford University Press, (2005).
- Kitchin, R. *The Data Revolution: Big Data, Open Data, Data Infrastructures, and their Consequences*. London: SAGE, (2014).
- Knight, J. *British Politics in Dummies*. London: Wiley, (2014).
- Mohan, J. *A United Kingdom: Economic, Social and Political Geographies*. London: Routledge, (2014).
- Heald, D. Transparency: The key to better governance? (No. 135). Oxford University Press, (2006): P.P. 91-107
- Public Administration Select Committee. *Statistics and Open Data: Harvesting Unused Knowledge, Empowering Citizens and Improving Public services* (HC 564). London: TSO, (2014).
- Reddick, C. 'Open government achievement and satisfaction in the U.S..' *Journal of E-Governance*, (2011): 34(4), 193- 202.
- Watts, D. *British Government and Politics*. London: Edinburgh University Press, (2012).
- Wessels, B. & Finn, R.. *Open Data and the Knowledge Society*. *Amsterdam University Press*, (2019).

Welch, E. W.' The Relationship between Transparent and Participative Government: A study of local governments in the United States'. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, (2012): 78(1), 93-115.

- White, N. Free and Frank: Making the Official Information Act Work Better. Wellington: Institute of Policy Studies. (2007).
- Wilson, D. J., & Game, C. Local Government in the United Kingdom. London: Macmillan (2011).
- Worthy, Ben 'Freedom of Information and the M.P.s' Expenses Scandal' in Hudson, J (ed.) At the Public's Expense? The Political Consequences of the 2009 British MPs' Expenses Scandal Palgrave, London, (2014): P.P. 27-43
- Bayer E., Thompson D., 2015. Communicating to advance the public's health: Workshop summary. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press, ISBN 978-0-309-36867-4
- Shabbir, T., M Nadeemullah, & Saeed Memon. (2020). Uses and Impact of 'Open Data' Technology for Developing Social Sector in Pakistan. Pakistan Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 1(1), 50-64. Retrieved from: <http://pjmr.org/pjmr/article/view/24>
- Buchanan, A.M, Gentile, D.A., Nelson, D.A., Walsh, D.A, Hensel, J (2002). What goes in must come out: Children's media violence consumption at home and aggressive behaviors at school. Minneapolis, MN: National Institute on Media and the Family.
- Nelson W.A. 2009, Handbook for Rural Health Care Ethics: A Practical Guide for Professionals, England, University Press of New England.
- Shabbir, T., Abro.M. (2019). Impact of 'Open Data' on 'News Media' and its Effectiveness in Social and Political Development of Pakistan (A Case Study from U.K. Perspective). *Dialogue*, 14(3), 161-171. Retrieved from <https://ideapublishers.org/index.php/lassij/article/view/163/99>
- GirlScoutResearchInstitute.(2002).Theneteffect:Girlsandnewmedia.NewYork:GirlScouts of theU.S.A.
- Shabbir, T., Mohsin, & Auj E Kamal. (2020). Use of 'Open Data' in Urdu Literature Research and its Effectiveness. *Liberal Arts and Social Sciences International Journal (LASSIJ)*, 4(1), 219-230. Retrieved from <http://journals.pu.edu.pk/journals/index.php/jms/article/viewFile/3734/1824>
- Valkenburg, P.M., PiotrowskiJ.T., 2017, pluggedin: How Media Attract and Affect Youth, New Haven, and London, Yale University PRESS, ISBN 978-0-300-21887-9

List of Journals

1. American Psychological Association

2. World-Bank

List of Newspapers

1. Financial Times
2. The New York Times